

Table A1. Model parameters

	Unit	Year		Sources and comments
		2015	2050	
Population	10 ⁶	8.630	9.771	Statistik Austria (2017a)
Floor space scenarios	m ² net floor space per person ⁽²⁾			
'Trend'		44.6	47.7	Assumption based on A. Müller et al. (2017) and Kalcher et al. (2016) (scenario 'moderate increase');
'Decline'			42.0	Adopted from Kalcher et al. (2016) (scenario 'moderate decline');
Wood construction scenarios				
Scenario 'Baseline'				Wood construction shares in 2010 and 2015 are inter-/extrapolated values based on Teischinger et al. (2015); shares after 2015 are scenario assumptions.
Wood construction share	%	22.0%	22.0%	
Average timber intensity ⁽¹⁾	m ³ /m ²	0.108	0.108	Timber intensities are based on wood construction shares and specific timber demand for typical buildings derived from the construction element database 'Baubook' (2017). The assumed average
Scenario 'Continued increase'				timber intensities of single-/two- and multi family-buildings are 0.23 m ³ /m ² gross floor space (single-/two-family) and 0.14 m ³ /m ² (multi-family) for wood construction, and 0.04 m ³ /m ² and 0.02 m ³ /m ² for conventional construction. The resulting average timber intensity over all RB in the base year 2015 is in
Wood construction share	%	22.0%	50.0%	good agreement with the average value for the timeframe 2001 to 2010 derived from Kalcher et al.
Average timber intensity ⁽¹⁾	m ³ /m ²	0.108	0.180	(2016): 0.10 m ³ /m ² .
Scenario 'Rapid increase'				
Wood construction share	%	22.0%	80.0%	
Average timber intensity ⁽¹⁾	m ³ /m ²	0.108	0.257	
Substitution factor scenarios				
'Default & dynamic'	GHG savings	142.9	28.6	Standard assumption derived from Hafner et al. (2017)
'High & dynamic'	in	200.0	40.0	
'Low & dynamic'	kg CO ₂ -equ.	93.3	18.7	Alternative assumptions (based on ranges according to Hafner et al. [2017]) assumed for sensitivity
'Default & constant'	per m ² net	142.9	142.9	analyses. Constant substitution factors are considered highly unlikely (grey font color).
'High & constant'	floor space	200.0	200.0	
'Low & constant'		93.3	93.3	

1) Timber intensity is measured in m³ of timber per m² net floor space. Data refer to the buildings constructed in the respective year, not the entire building stock.

2) Default ratio net to gross floor space: 0.7; Assumptions for sensitivity analyses regarding substitution factors: 0.65 to 0.75

Appendix to 'Carbon dynamics and GHG implications of increasing wood construction:
Long-term scenarios for residential buildings in Austria'

Table A2. Cumulated GHG savings during 2015 to 2050 in all scenarios and sensitivity analyses (Unit: Mt CO₂-equ.). The most relevant results, which are also referred to in the abstract, are highlighted in yellow.

Wood construction scenario	Substitution factor scenario	Living space scenario	Cumulated GHG savings from material substitution effect during 2015 to 2050		Total cumulated GHG savings 2015 to 2050	
			Savings	Difference to respective 'Baseline' scenario	Savings	Difference to respective 'Baseline' scenario
Main scenarios						
'Baseline'	'Default & dynamic'	'Trend'	4.89	-	17.32	-
		'Decline'	3.85	-	10.74	-
'Continued increase'	'Default & dynamic'	'Trend'	7.89	3.00	29.55	12.23
		'Decline'	6.04	2.19	19.54	8.80
'Rapid increase'	'Default & dynamic'	'Trend'	10.96	6.07	42.22	24.90
		'Decline'	8.27	4.42	28.63	17.89
Sensitivity analyses						
'Baseline'	'Low & dynamic'	'Trend'	3.19	-	15.63	-
		'Decline'	2.52	-	9.41	-
	'High & dynamic'	'Trend'	6.84	-	19.28	-
		'Decline'	5.39	-	12.28	-
	'Default & constant'	'Trend'	8.05	-	20.49	-
		'Decline'	7.38	-	14.27	-
	'Low & constant'	'Trend'	5.26	-	17.70	-
		'Decline'	3.99	-	10.88	-
	'High & constant'	'Trend'	11.27	-	23.71	-
		'Decline'	8.54	-	15.44	-
'Continued increase'	'Low & dynamic'	'Trend'	5.15	1.96	26.82	11.19
		'Decline'	3.94	1.43	17.45	8.04
	'High & dynamic'	'Trend'	11.04	4.20	32.71	13.43
		'Decline'	8.45	3.06	21.95	9.67
	'Default & constant'	'Trend'	14.24	6.18	35.91	15.42
		'Decline'	12.92	5.54	26.42	12.15
	'Low & constant'	'Trend'	9.30	4.04	30.97	13.27
		'Decline'	6.88	2.89	20.38	9.50
	'High & constant'	'Trend'	19.93	8.66	41.60	17.89
		'Decline'	14.74	6.19	28.24	12.80
'Rapid increase'	'Low & dynamic'	'Trend'	7.16	3.97	38.42	22.79
		'Decline'	5.40	2.89	25.76	16.35
	'High & dynamic'	'Trend'	15.34	8.50	46.60	27.33
		'Decline'	11.58	6.19	31.94	19.65
	'Default & constant'	'Trend'	20.66	12.61	51.92	31.43
		'Decline'	18.66	11.28	39.02	24.75
	'Low & constant'	'Trend'	13.50	8.24	44.76	27.06
		'Decline'	9.87	5.88	30.23	19.35
	'High & constant'	'Trend'	28.93	17.65	60.19	36.48
		'Decline'	21.15	12.61	41.51	26.07